

New viewpoint in Physics

(Gravitation principle And We can made the ufo)

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Introduction: explains the principle of motion, the principle of universal gravitation from the perspective of relative space, deduces two models of dark matter particles and the model of antigravity, deduces the phenomenon of violating the law of conservation of energy from antigravity, and redefines the potential energy.

Keywords: principle of gravity, antigravity principle

1. Preamble

Ten years ago I wrote several small articles explaining the principle of gravity, ways to overcome gravity, kinetic energy, potential energy, the nature of the law of conservation of energy, the two-particle model of dark matter, gravitational waves, the speed of light and other issues, proposing their internal laws and forming a theoretical system. With the passage of time and deeper thinking it was finally confirmed that these elements are undoubtedly correct. On the other hand, there has been no breakthrough in the understanding of the problem of the interaction between the gravity field and space, which has become a flaw in the theoretical system, affecting one's understanding of the entire universe.

The process of thinking and writing is so long that it took me more than ten years from the beginning of the process to the solution of the last problem currently in mind. Recently, I have solved the difficult problem of the role of gravity fields (gravitational fields) in relation to relative space through constant reflection, and my understanding of the universe is more complete than before, and forms a perfect corroboration with my previous theories. So with the new understanding, I reread a few short articles I had originally written, and realized that while they explained some of the problems, they lacked a more systematic and detailed explanation among them, and the logical sequence was not smooth enough to make them comprehensible. In order to explain more clearly, it was decided to rewrite the article into a more detailed one.

In sorting out the ideas for the rewritten article, it always seemed that I was not systematically trained in physics theories and ways of thinking, and had no way of explaining my theories with the tools available. One has to create something of one's own, including a handful of new words, novel ideas, etc., which are rubbed together and are about to form a strange article. Based on the inertia that everyone has, it will be very difficult for people to accept this content that I have self-invented.

The scope of my thinking is broad, but based on this and writing a large and comprehensive article is impossible, upon reflection, my own theory turned out to be so simple that it is not even worth to use too much space to explain. Although it is simple, as long as one understands the key points, everything can be connected in a natural way. Connected things include certain basic principles in physics, through in these basic principles, can open up a wide space for you, give you endless resources, stimulate your selfless thoughts, and then go deeper, will point directly to the true nature of self-nature, very naturally towards Buddhism.

2. Relative Space

It has always been assumed that contemporary physics has solved most of the problems and is moving in a more microscopic and macroscopic direction. However, in the process of thinking about the phenomena of physics, I found that the phenomenon of "motion" is so common that people treat it as common sense, and there is no clear explanation of the nature of the motion of matter in contemporary physics, and the description of the motion is only limited to the relativity of the motion, inertia and energy changes, etc., and it is not explained from a deeper perspective. There is no deeper explanation. It was this discovery that prompted me to start thinking deeply, and in the beginning, I did not even think about why I was doing this. It was not until I went deeper into it and went farther out and discovered the decisive role of relative space in the physical phenomena it involved that I realized that starting to think about this problem had undoubtedly put me on the right path. It was arduous, but from the moment of clarity one had seen the light, and it was only by seeing the light that one realized the importance of thinking in this way.

So why is it necessary to think deeply about such an all-too-common phenomenon?

For one thing, motion is the most common physical phenomenon in the universe, and a mere superficial understanding of such a common phenomenon is incomplete.

Secondly, the phenomenon of motion is the basis of all physical phenomena, and without in-depth thinking, it will be impossible to have a deeper understanding of energy, and it will also be impossible to explain gravity adequately.

Now that we have discovered what the problem is, we need to think deeply. It was very difficult at first, not having found a ready-made method, and not knowing whether I was thinking in the right direction or not. So with all the concepts related to the movement, I started in a chaos, slowly clearing up the chaotic thinking, and persisting, persisting again and again, solely on the basis of my own conviction and relentlessness. This is not obsession or paranoia, but because of one's own belief that any question, if pursued to the extreme, must be consistent with the fundamental truths of the universe, rather than diverging from them.

Thankfully with one's persistence, a method finally presented itself in front of one's eyes - relative space. This method is so simple. Of course I now know that this was the result of personal obstacles and foolishness that made this method and truth, despite being so obvious and simple, years of searching in bewildered contemplation.

Here is how I did it: Imagine that in an ideal vacuum space there are two identical particles, one at rest and the other moving at a certain speed relative to the former. Under this assumption keep making ideal observations of the two particles.

In this process, I had strictly in accordance with the special relativity, general relativity, quantum mechanics to compare, but always feel that there is a little bit imperfect, or, always feel a little bit strange, of course, this is only a very simple intuition. So it kept insisting on thinking in its own way.

And so it went on for about five years. Suddenly one day I had this vision in front of my eyes that two particles could not be regarded as just very small particles, but that they had to be regarded as existing with a certain space in which the electromagnetic waves contained in the particles were moving at the speed of light. The reason for the change in energy between the two is due to the redshift and blueshift phenomenon that exists when the electromagnetic wave transitions from its relative space to the relative space of the other particle.

Continuing to build on this discovery, and considering this discovery over and over again in the context of the macroscopic and microscopic phenomena of the universe known to him, more questions gradually became clearer. More physical phenomena appeared because of relative space, such as what electromagnetic waves are, what energy is, what gravity is all about, what the law of conservation of energy is all about, the concepts of relative and absolute space, etc. Finally, I further understood that what really exists in the universe is the relativity of space (or called space compression), not time relativity. Time is merely an artificial measure of change in space, not real existence. Based on spatial relativity and spatial drag, it is satisfied that "the laws of physics have the same form in all inertial systems"

and that "the speed of propagation of light in vacuum has the same value C in all inertial systems".

Now I know that even without considering the interior of particles, relative space is widespread in the universe, all around us.

It is a bit difficult to explain the concept of relative space alone; it is included in the nature of motion, the nature of energy, the nature of gravity, and the nature of particles, which I will present in the next pages in conjunction with the concept of relative space.

3. The Nature of Movement

I have found that the simpler it is the closer it gets to the truth.

Of course, it is difficult to get people to accept this idea that goes against all previous knowledge. But it might be worth a try.

Here's how I see it: think of particles as beings with a certain amount of space in which the internal structure of the particle is the basis for the physical properties that the particle develops in relative motion. In the particle model I constructed, all contained electromagnetic waves move at the speed of light inside the particle, and the reason for that conclusion is that space is relative. On this basis the nature of motion can be discovered. As shown in Fig. 1:

Figure 1

In Fig. 1, assume that particle A is relatively stationary and particle B is moving with velocity v relative to particle A. If any of the particles are taken out and viewed separately, there is no difference between them.

But when the two particles are viewed relative to each other, there is a conversion of the relative space, as shown in the figure, when the electromagnetic wave in particle B is converted to the relative space of particle A, in the direction of v, the head of a beam of electromagnetic wave leaves particle B, and the rest of the electromagnetic wave is still moving forward with v. Then when the electromagnetic wave leaves particle B in its entirety, the wavelength appears to be compressed in the v direction. In the opposite direction of v there is a stretching of the wavelength.

During this transition, W2 appears to change in wavelength and frequency relative to W1:

$$\text{Wavelength of W1 and W2: } \lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right) \quad \lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \times \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)$$

$$\text{Frequency of W1 and W2: } \gamma_1 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c-v} \quad \gamma_2 = \gamma_0 \times \frac{c}{c+v}$$

The total energy of particle B with respect to particle A can be considered as ,then:

$$E_b = h \cdot \gamma_1 + h \cdot \gamma_2 = h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c-v} + h \cdot \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{c}{c+v}$$

Particle B is redshifted relative to particle A (or blueshifted if two particles are moving relative to each other), then particle B exhibits a change in kinetic energy relative to particle A.

When the velocity v approaches the speed of light, the kinetic energy of particle B relative to particle A will approach infinity. Of course, the same is true for particle A relative to particle B.

They differ only in the change in overall energy in different relative spaces.

4. The first particle model of dark matter

In this theoretical system that I have discovered, relative space is the basis for many fundamental physical principles, including the formation of particles, and particles are not just a quantum issue in traditional physics.

In thinking about the nature of motion in the above way, it is inevitable that a special case will be found, that is, when in a particle, the relative space in which the particle is formed is a plane, and all electromagnetic waves propagate in this plane. Then, when the particle moves in a direction perpendicular to this plane, there is no change in energy. As in Figure 2:

Figure 2

The reason for this is that for each copy of the electromagnetic wave, there is no change in the wavelength and frequency of the electromagnetic wave as it leaves the relative space of that particle and enters some other relative space.

Further study on this basis reveals that there is no effect of inertia of this particle in the direction perpendicular to this plane. Thus the nature of inertia is slowly revealed. But it cannot be summarized in this chapter yet, because there is an important concept that has not been elaborated yet and is left to be explained in the appropriate chapter for the time being.

The reason I describe this particle model as one of the particle models of dark matter is that, because this particle moves in this direction of motion, there is no change in energy, is not affected by inertia, and can reach higher velocities with relative ease, thus making it less susceptible to being controlled by a gravitational field.

The second particle model I have defined produces the ability to be fundamentally able to resist the force of gravity as opposed to the previously described particle model. To explain that particle model and its principles, it is necessary to first figure out exactly what kind of force gravity is - what is the principle of gravity?

5. The principle of gravity

M1 and M2 are two relatively stationary particles. In M1 and M2, the internal electromagnetic waves propagate at the speed of light in their own spatial system, and there is no interaction when they are observed individually (Fig. 3).

Figure 3

When M1 and M2 are observed together, the electromagnetic waves inside M2 show a change in the density of the relative space with respect to the relative space of M1 (Fig. 4):

Figure 4

In the direction toward M1, the density of the electromagnetic waves in M2 relative to the relative space of M1 increases with time;

In the direction away from M1, the density of the electromagnetic waves of M2 relative to the relative space of M1 decreases with time.

Electromagnetic waves of M2 relative to the relative space of M1 produce an overall difference in the tendency to M1 - the electromagnetic waves of M2 passing through the relative space belonging to M1 are sparse away from M1 and dense near M1.

This tendency creates an energy difference that tends toward M1, and it is this that leads to gravity. When the perspectives of M1 and M2 are swapped the result remains the same.

The more electromagnetic waves there are in M2, the more mass there is, the greater the energy difference; the more electromagnetic waves there are in M1, the greater the density of action on outer space, the stronger the force of gravity. The same is true for the electromagnetic waves in M1 relative to M2; a change in the number of electromagnetic waves in either M1 or M2 leads to a change in gravity.

According to this principle, the objects on the earth are attracted by the gravitational force of the earth because the particles constituting the earth have their "relative spatial effects" superimposed on each other, forming the overall relative spatial effects. The electromagnetic waves in the relative space of the particles that make up the object have an overall tendency to move toward the Earth due to the difference in density of the relative space action of the Earth as a whole.

As shown in Fig. 5, the action space of M1 forms a sphere with radius R at different distances R. If the density of spatial action is defined to be p on the sphere of M1, the density of spatial action at distance R is p/R^2 , that is to say, gravity at distances where the radius of the particles can be neglected has a magnitude that is: directly proportional to the number of electromagnetic waves in M1 and M2, and inversely proportional to the distance between them as the square is inversely proportional. This is often referred to as the fundamental reason for the gravitational force formula.

Figure 5

The above is the principle of gravity.

People believe that the reason for gravity is due to gravitational waves, gravitational changes will occur when the spatial action to fluctuations in the process of outward propagation, but gravitational waves are not the fundamental principle of gravity, it is a one-way action.

Electromagnetic waves in particles and the relative space of particles as a whole, there is a "relative spatial effect" on the external space. This relative action cannot exceed the speed of light. When a particle is created, its effect on

space propagates at the speed of light, and when this effect propagates to other particles, the other particles begin to be attracted by the gravitational force of the particle. If the "spatial action" of the other particles already existed before the particle was created, at the location where the particle was created, the particle is immediately subject to the gravitational pull of the other particles from the moment of its creation. The other particles will not be gravitated by the other particles until the spatial action of the particle has propagated to the position of the other particles. Gravity is not always mutual, depending on the existence and propagation of the "spatial interaction". The previous definition of "gravitational wave" is inaccurate, because one of the reasons is that the spatial action exists and propagates not always the gravitational force, and the second reason is that the gravitational wave does not visualize the cause of the gravitational force.

"Spatial effects" propagate at the speed of light, and spatial effects are the effects of "changes in relative space" in space on different relative spaces. When light from a distant galaxy reaches the Earth, its "spatial action" begins to act on the Earth, and gravity acts on the Earth. The "spatial effect" is always relative, and the spatial effect is not necessarily the same for different particles, so it should be called "relative spatial effect".

Changes in "spatial action" and "relative spatial action" are themselves spatial changes.

In describing the nature of motion and the nature of gravity, there is a key difference between the two relative space: the existence of gravity is based on the relative spatial action of one particle with respect to another, and the relative space of the two is superimposed on each other, which is different from the motion, so there is no need for the conversion of relative space. The existence or non-existence of gravity cannot take into account mutual motion. That is, even if two particles, one of which is moving at the speed of light relative to the other, either close or far away, the gravitational force between the two of them does not disappear as a result of this motion.

When thinking about the cause of gravity, there is a misconception that must be avoided: defining the curvature of space by the existence of gravity, and then deducing gravity from the curvature. This will logically create a complete mutual derivation. Gravity, curvature, curvature, and gravity invert each other, and falsehoods abound, confusing forever.

At the same time, the principle of gravity, as described in this chapter, does not mean that space is flat or unchanging, for there is a premise: "relative" spatial action - gravity for ordinary particles, and perhaps repulsion for special particles.

6. Ways to overcome gravity and the second particle model of dark matter

Methods of overcoming the force of gravity can be deduced by continuing to derive ideas based on the concepts of relative space, relative spatial action, and the overall trend of relative spatial action.

Of course, the rotation of artificial Earth satellites around the Earth is one of the well-known methods.

We generally overcome gravity by circular or elliptical motion, and we say that circular or elliptical motion produces centrifugal force, but how does centrifugal force come about?

The principle can be analyzed by the above method. In Figure 6-1, M1 and M2 are two identical particles, and M2 moves around M1 with velocity v in a uniform circular motion. To analyze why M2 can obtain centrifugal force by using circular motion, it is necessary to convert the electromagnetic wave of M2 to the relative space of M1.

As shown in Figure 6-2, in the process of conversion, the wavelength of the electromagnetic wave W1 becomes longer and the wavelength of the electromagnetic wave W2 becomes shorter. Thus the frequency of the electromagnetic wave W1 becomes slower and the energy decreases; the frequency of W2 becomes faster and the energy increases.

As shown in Figure 6-3, in the direction of the velocity v , an overall energy difference is produced, and this energy difference is moving away from the space of action of M1 from time to time, so that M2 has a tendency to move away from M1, which is the centrifugal force, that is, the reason why the gravitational force can be overcome by circular or

elliptical motion.

Continuing the reasoning, a second method of overcoming the force of gravity can be obtained.

Suppose A is a circular plane particle with all electromagnetic waves propagating rotationally around the edge. B is an ordinary particle on a plumb line through the center of A (Figure 7-1). At any moment on particle A, the direction of the electromagnetic wave is tangential to the edge of particle A (Figure 7-2).

Observation of the spatial state of A and B shows that at any moment, the propagation direction of the electromagnetic wave in particle A is on the tangent line of the action space of B (Figure 7-3). Relative to the relative action space of B, the electromagnetic wave in particle A forms an outward energy difference, which produces an action away from the center of mass of B. That is, the force between A and B is repulsive!

The space action of particle B on the outside is different from the action of different particles, so it should be called "relative space action".

Particle A is one of the particle models of dark matter. This particle, while moving in the vertical line of its plane, is not affected by inertia and can exceed the speed of light due to the repulsive force with the star, provided that the spatial action of the star is already present in the space through which the particle passes. On the other hand, the existence of repulsive action between such a particle and other particles, and the greater the repulsive force the closer the particle is, makes it difficult for it to collide with other particles even if it is moving at a very high speed, and it can even pass through dense solids with ease. This is the perfect explanation for the FTL neutrino phenomenon, i.e., it explains the principle of neutrino action and also explains the FTL phenomenon.

I had closely followed the discovery of FTL neutrinos by the European Center for Nuclear Research (CERN) in 2011, and unfortunately the publicly available information shows that the tests were a failure. But my theory supports them.

One can mimic this particle model to overcome gravity.

As in Figure 8, a superconducting coil is wrapped around a horizontal circular plane that can rotate around a vertical axis and held in place. By introducing a certain amount of electrical energy, a lifting force opposite to the direction of gravity is generated.

Figure 8

The lift is proportional to the square of the radius of the coil, proportional to the energy transferred, and inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the center of mass of the star (note: experimental verification is required).

The key to all the ways we are going to overcome gravity is to be able to create an overall energy difference along the spherical tangent of the star's space of action, creating a tendency to move away.

The above explains EMDRIVE (Impulsive Thrust from a Closed Radio-Frequency Cavity in Vacuum) very well. The content of the article seems to be simple, but in reality, it is to remove the complexity and keep the simplicity. There is an old Chinese saying "The Great Taoist Way is the simplest way", and this is exactly what is happening here.

Predictably, when the energy input is large enough, a force greater than gravity can be generated to accelerate the device away from Earth, making space travel over large distances a simple matter. Legendary flying saucers, if they really exist, must have gotten their force to overcome gravity in this way.

In a previous article I wrote, I described it this way: "The reason a flying saucer can generate power: no matter how an object moves, as long as it is within the spatial range of another object's action, its quantum of spatial variation will be affected by the density of the other object's action space. The only way to overcome this effect is for an object to produce a difference in the number of quanta of spatial variation that can be moved away from the space of action of the other object at any given moment" (the concept of "quanta of spatial variation" is not taken into account in this description for the time being, but I will introduce and explain it later on in this article).

When the energy of the flying saucer increases to a certain level, a repulsive force greater than the gravitational force will be generated at any location in space, and the flying saucer will accelerate away from the Earth. Predictably, to overcome gravity, the energy input to the coil must exceed the kinetic energy possessed to overcome the first cosmic velocity. When the flying saucer leaves the gravitational range of the Earth, the same methods described above can be used to overcome the gravitational pull of even more powerful planets, or even galaxies, on the way to true interstellar freedom. As long as the flying saucer's energy is high enough to keep accelerating at a consistently high rate to move away from the Earth, and to keep accelerating at a consistently high rate to slow down when it reaches its destination, then it can travel from the Earth to the Moon in just a few minutes, and to Mars in just a few tens of hours, or even less.

What is special about this force: one, it does not require throwing matter to realize the reaction force, which would violate the law of conservation of momentum if it were not explained with this theory I have provided; and two, the speed of moving away would increase with time as the effect of the force of gravity is overcome, at which point the increase in speed would not require the expenditure of more energy. This kind of motion will fundamentally impact the traditional kinetic energy - potential energy theory system, and produce irreconcilable contradictions with the most important law in traditional physics - the law of conservation of energy.

The reason for this contradiction is, firstly, that the concept of "relative spatial action" has not been introduced into the law of conservation of energy. Secondly, if we continue to explore the law of conservation of energy, we will find that it is not that energy is not conserved, but that the law of conservation of energy has certain limitations - it does not define and explain kinetic energy and potential energy in a deeper sense. And to explain kinetic and potential energy requires a deeper understanding of electromagnetic waves and their relative space.

7. Space change quantum, space system

In order to better explain kinetic energy and potential energy, and to describe the law of conservation of energy at a deeper level, it is necessary to introduce several new concepts: quanta of spatial variation, spatial system.

The origin of matter in the universe comes from spatial variation. Spatial variation, in turn, is able to summarize all matter in the universe, visible and invisible matter or particles, and their motion or otherwise. Matter in this context includes dark matter, anti-matter.

Electromagnetic waves are essentially spatial changes, a cycle of change-blocking-change in space.

Space to produce a certain point of change, the change is located in the relative space, the properties of space has a role in maintaining the change will prevent the change to produce, and prevent itself is change, and a new change to prevent it, resulting in the propagation of spatial change spread, "change - blocking" This process of "change-block" can be regarded as a quantum, which I call "space change quantum", and it constitutes the electromagnetic wave.

When the wavelength of electromagnetic wave becomes shorter and the frequency becomes faster, the essence is that in the relative space where the electromagnetic wave is located, the number of spatial changes increases, and the essence is the increase of spatial change quantum. In the relative space where the electromagnetic wave is located, the number of spatial changes increases, resulting in an increase in the frequency of the electromagnetic wave.

The increase in the number of spatial variations to a certain point leads to a sharp change in space at that point, forming a curved space within which spatial variations are confined to form particles. Within the particle, the spatial variation does not stop, but propagates at the speed of light within a certain range.

The spatial change quanta and the relative space in which they are located constitute the overall spatial system.

In the same way as the principle of propagation of space-varying quanta because of stopping, the spatial system, the particle, has a maintaining effect on its own spatial properties; on the basis of this effect, to change the state of motion of the particle, it is necessary to exert an influence on it.

The change in the state of motion of a particle is essentially a change in the relative quantity of the quanta of spatial change as they are transformed between different relative spaces. Changes in relative quantities are also changes in space.

The reason that a spatial system has a holding effect on its own spatial properties is that changes in the number of spatially varying quanta within a relative space cannot occur on their own.

Under the perspective of relative space, the nature of inertia and kinetic energy can be found, and the definition of mass, including inertial mass and gravitational mass, can also be deduced.

Look at Figure 1 again: an overall change in density occurs as the quantum of space change in particle B is converted to the relative space of particle A. The fundamental difference between particle B and particle A is the change in the overall density of space-varying quanta that occurs in the direction of relative motion in the relative space in which they are moving, as well as the change in the frequency of space-varying quanta formed in the process of conversion of different relative spaces to each other, and the change in frequency is essentially a change in the number of space-varying quanta. At the same time, the change in the relative number of space-varying quanta of both particles A and B is also a change in relative space.

These two particles of the relative number of spatial change quanta are different, in order to make the two particles converge, must exert influence, change the relative number of spatial change quanta of one of the parties, so that the two spatial change quanta converge. The process of change is the process of doing work. The process of doing work is essentially the conversion of the quanta of spatial variation in one spatial system to another. If particle A is allowed to reach the state of particle B, a force needs to be applied to particle A to bring particle A to the speed of particle B's motion. This force applied will be directly converted in particle A to the spatial change quanta of particle A, causing the overall number of spatial change quanta of A to change.

Without the process of doing work, the spatial change quanta in the spatial system would not change and the

spatial properties of the spatial system would remain. The ability of the spatial system to maintain its spatial properties is the inertia of the spatial system.

The essence of energy is the number of spatial change quanta in the spatial system, and the external manifestation is the part of the change in the number of spatial change quanta. The process of doing work on a spatial system is essentially the process of changing the number of spatially varying quanta in the spatial system. --This explains the nature of energy only in terms of relative motion, which one defines as kinetic energy.

The relative space of a particle with its contained quanta of spatial change constitutes a spatial system, and the change in the overall number of quanta of spatial change in that spatial system cannot occur by itself, and the external manifestation is the holding effect of the spatial system on the properties of space, which will prevent the change in the state of motion of the spatial system, and the value of the ability to prevent the change is the inertial mass. The magnitude of this capacity value depends on the overall number of spatial change quanta within the spatial system.

Note: Although describing the quanta of spatial change can be completely replaced by electromagnetic waves, I think it is still necessary to introduce the concept of quanta of spatial change. This is because it is also the only way to essentially expound on electromagnetic waves, and the only way to describe the related concepts in a unified manner.

8. Potential energy

Potential energy and kinetic energy are different in nature, and in order to distinguish between them, we need to explore the effect of gravity on the spatial system more deeply.

Let's look at "Figure 4", when M1, M2 is far away from each other, the relative spatial action of the two angles are small, either side of the overall number of spatial change quantum relative to the other side of the offset is small. When the two are close together, the angle of spatial action gradually increases, and so does the offset, showing different degrees of offset at different distances. This difference constitutes a difference in potential energy at the same time that the gravitational force increases with decreasing distance.

The change in the potential energy of a particle is caused by the difference in the degree of imbalance of the spatially varying quanta in the particle relative to another spatial system at different spatial distances. Relative to the earth's action space, the lower the ground, the greater this relative imbalance, the smaller the potential energy; in a higher position the relative imbalance is smaller, the greater the potential energy.

This is an essential discussion of potential energy, which does not contradict the quantitative description of potential energy. Our definition of potential energy is, in the final analysis, the difference between quanta of spatial change relative to different spaces of action at different heights from the ground.

At a certain altitude, this relative spatial imbalance is at a certain level, and if the altitude is changed, a change in the degree of imbalance is inevitably induced. Due to the space occupied by the particle and the contained space change quantum composed of space system on the spatial properties of the maintenance of the role, will prevent the change, which is the gravitational mass. Gravitational mass and inertial mass, both of which are the ability of the spatial system to maintain its own spatial properties, are fundamentally the relative number of spatially varying quanta - a unified description of gravitational mass and inertial mass.

In overcoming the force of gravity would fundamentally shake up the traditional law of conservation of energy. In this problem, it is not that energy is no longer conserved, but that the definitions of kinetic and potential energy in traditional physics are problematic.

The process of converting potential energy into kinetic energy is essentially to use the force of gravity as a medium to convert the "change in the degree of imbalance" in the "overall number of spatially varying quanta of change" into the direction of particle motion, resulting in a change in the number of spatially varying quanta of a spatial system, that is, the change in kinetic energy, which is the change of kinetic energy. The change in the number of spatially varying quanta in a spatial system is the change in kinetic energy.

This change is reversed by the force that overcomes the gravitational force, or by the antigravitational force. In this process, the potential energy increases while the kinetic energy will increase, which violates the law of conservation of energy, but this is not an error. In essence, it is the change in the overall number of spatially varying quanta in the "change in the degree of imbalance" that is transformed into the direction of motion of the particles by the antigravity force, resulting in the change in the number of spatially varying quanta of a certain spatial system, that is, the change in the kinetic energy.

The spatial system that causes antigravity has the opposite relative spatial effect to the spatial system where gravity exists.

That is, in the change of the degree of relative spatial imbalance, it is necessary to take into account the influence of the direction of the relative spatial action on both sides of the particle. With the difference in the direction of the relative spatial action, in the process of changing the degree of imbalance, the increase or decrease of the degree of imbalance can make the kinetic energy increase or decrease. The degree of imbalance of the spatially changing quanta in the relative spatial density is the potential energy. The author believes that such a description of kinetic energy and potential energy is still not rigorous enough in the definition of the future need more people through more in-depth research to obtain a rigorous description.

9. Electromagnetic wave propagation based on space itself

There is a concept that has not been specifically mentioned in the previous chapters, because its significance has been implied in the text: the propagation of electromagnetic waves is based on space itself, and does not require a medium other than space. (The term "space" in this context refers to the absolute vacuum).

That is to say, while a little change in space is generated, space keeps its own properties, and a little new change must be generated to stop the previous change, and then a newer change will be generated to stop it. The "quantum of space change" is in the process of "change - stop (change) - change (stop)" cycle. In the process of propagation, all that is needed is space itself, and no other medium is necessary.

This statement is only formally similar to the "Ether theory" before the beginning of the twentieth century, but the essence is completely different. The "Ether" was only imagined as a continuous medium in which electromagnetic waves could propagate.

As a separate spatial system, the medium may have different spatial properties (or states of motion) from the cosmic space. In the propagation of "space-varying quanta", if it enters the medium, it immediately changes to propagate in the medium, and when it propagates in the medium, it completely follows the spatial properties of the medium, and the propagation speed depends on the spatial properties of the medium. If the medium advances at a certain speed, then the propagation speed relative to the cosmic space is the superposition of the propagation speed in the medium and the speed of the medium's motion.

Since the medium is not necessary for the propagation of "space-varying quanta", and space itself is difficult to measure, how to determine the propagation speed of "space-varying quanta" in the cosmic space? So the question comes back to the measurement of the speed of light.

The process of "change-blocking" of "space-varying quanta" is the reason for the existence of energy in the universe. Due to the existence of the process of "change-blocking", the "space change quantum", cosmic space, particle space and other different ranges and sizes of the space system "The ability to maintain their spatial properties throughout the universe is a prerequisite for the existence of inertia and mass in matter.

10. A New View of the Universe

Since the creation of the universe, its space has been changing continuously, and every bit of space change is a

"quantum of space change". The "creation of space" is itself a "change of space", and every bit of space created by the expansion of the universe is a new change of space.

The universe could have exploded at superluminal speed from an infinitesimal point, and while space was created, space itself prevented the creation of space, and new quanta of space change appeared, and the superluminal speed made the quanta of space change extremely dense. Going further, the universe was born from nothing. Even deeper, the universe was not created by the Big Bang, but from the philosophical sense of "confusion", as opposed to "confusion" is "consciousness".

Note: My English is not worth mentioning. Please understand that I have already felt overwhelmed by the translation, especially some philosophical or religious terms, and I will not translate any additional content. At the same time, the content that has been translated must also be miserable, although I once looked for a professional translation agency to help me translate, but it is also not ideal, because in my neighborhood English is more professional and well versed in physics there is really no one, but in order to disseminate my insights will have to be so, forgive me.

Space itself prevents space from being created, but it can only affect the space that has been created, not the expansion of the edges of the universe. Until now, the expansion of the universe has not slowed down, generating new space at the edges, generating new quanta of spatial change, while the spatial change within is still propagating and continuing.

The real situation is that when you measure the edge of the universe, but you see a much wider universe. In other words, the universe is now infinite in scale and mass, but the speed of light limitations on the propagation of spatial change quanta prevents us from seeing more.

Humans can never see the center of the universe, or there is no center, while it can be said that everywhere is the center, which is inseparable from the drag effect of electromagnetism relative to space.

Multiple copies of the space change quantum to form an electromagnetic wave, with the increase in the number of quanta, the drag on its own relative space increases, gradually from the spherical propagation into conical propagation, and then into a straight line propagation, and finally, a large number of space changes in the quantum of its own relative space to produce extreme drag, the formation of a closed "quantum space". Quantum space and everything within it is a particle.

Without the drag of electromagnetic relative space, no particles would emerge, and the universe would be a mass of electromagnetic waves.

With the creation of particles comes matter and gravity, and the matter within a certain range is dragged together by gravity to form nebulae, stars, and black holes.

A black hole is an extreme celestial body, which is dragged extremely relative to space, forming a closed space within a certain range, and everything is included in this space, which is somewhat like a super-giant particle.

Suffice it to say that whereas a normal celestial body produces only a tiny drag on electromagnetic relative space, a black hole produces an extreme drag, which, according to the principle of gravity described earlier, causes the space inside the black hole to form a closed loop under this extreme drag. The absence of gravity between the two black holes, while ignoring the matter pulled by the outside of the black holes, allows the universe to expand externally while the inside is divided into many smaller parts and stabilized. This is the only way to keep the universe from becoming an unstable object that is constantly expanding on the outside, but collapsing and exploding on the inside.

The soul of life, centripetal and centrifugal, following gravity will sink and counter-gravity will rise. Under the action of anti-gravity, the future of mankind will surely become a life with unlimited space, unlimited resources, unlimited thoughts, everything is unlimited, the only limitation is its own evil,- any kind of life is, including robots. You have to think about who you were before you came to this world. --The Buddha's classics have told you that it is your true self-nature, and we need to realize our true nature and benefit all beings.

Goodness should permeate every corner. The fundamental truth of the universe must be good, promising,

compatible with fraternity, and eternal, not the darkness that represents death or the flames and explosions that represent destruction. All theories that deduce the future of mankind as death and destruction are based on selfish and narrow-minded ideas and misinterpret the basic truth of the universe.

Some of what has been written before is systematic, some is said wherever it occurs to me, and there are still many questions to be solved, and no end to them, as they lead along the line of thought. Let's leave it at that for now.

I'll end with a few more epiphanies from the thinking process.

Looking back on those years of thinking, it was all chance, and in chance it led to the right path. Combined with the sutras I have read now, I realize that everything is karma, and that what I am thinking about is "movement and stillness," and now I have been able to realize that the two phases of movement and stillness do not come into being. So I summarize this process as follows: Karma arises from motion and stillness.

Looking at the entire theoretical system, all explanations will eventually lead to the fundamental truths of the universe. And it is very likely that these truths have already been discussed by the ancient sages in the classics. That is to say, the ancient sages have been waiting for us on the other side of the shore, while we are still in the self-proclaimed "science" in the ocean to follow the current.

Of course, the classics of the sages had to fit the language and learning environment of the sages at that time, and could not be described in our present language, and the further back in time they are, the more difficult it is to understand them. Carefully discerning my thinking process can also be found in the classics described by the sages, so I'm going to start this article with a long-winded talk about my own thinking process and reasoning, which is to illustrate that we must not ignore the classics because they are difficult to understand before thoroughly comprehending them.

Around the beginning of October 2017, I was again thinking about why two identical particles why the relative spatial action is different simply because of the difference in spatial location, that is, why the relative spatial action affects other particles, a question which for the time being appears to be unanswerable. If we have to explain, we can find some reasons from the generation of fluctuations and the formation of particles, the smallest fluctuations are propagated in all directions, its space is large; large fluctuations are formed into particles, its space is small; particles are formed by the fluctuation changes in the small amount of space circled by the vast cosmic space is actually still one, only relative to the fluctuations formed by the closed space, relative to the space itself is still the whole! Part of space, there is no obstacle to space itself.

In this sense, the ancient sages have already made corresponding statements, among which are the classics of Buddhism and Taoism. Motion is the same solution. Energy is the same solution. Fluctuation is the same solution. It all starts here!

Now, I have explained the above scientific theories with the "Law of Non-Wealth" and guided them into the realm of "Non-Wealth". I have scientifically proven the "Law of Nothing" in the Buddhist and Taoist classics, and proved the correctness of the Law of Nothing. More scientific theories can be explained from the perspective revealed in this text.

The Way is simple! But if you cannot realize the Way, you will never be able to understand it.